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● Catalogue of *Callispa* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Cassidinae) from Guangdong Province of China, with redescription of a new provincial recorded species

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Abstract: *Callispa dimidiatipennis* Baly, 1858 is recorded from Guangdong Province of China for the first time. A comprehensive redescription of the species is provided, accompanied by illustrations of diagnostic features. Furthermore, a catalogue of eight *Callispa* species known from Guangdong and a key to these species are presented.

Keywords: Chrysomeloidea, Callispini, taxonomy, key, China

● 广东省丽甲属 *Callispa* 名录及一新记录种再描述（鞘翅目：叶甲科：龟甲亚科）

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摘要: 本文记录了广东省龟甲亚科丽甲族一新记录种：半鞘丽甲 *Callispa dimidiatipennis* Baly, 1858。提供了该新记录种详细的重描述、特征图以及广东省丽甲属名录以及 8 个物种的分种检索表。

关键词: 叶甲科，丽甲族，分类学，检索表，中国

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● Introduction

The genus *Callispa* Baly, 1858 includes approximately 174 species found across the Oriental and Afrotropical regions (Staines 2015; Sekerka & Świętojańska 2024). These species are primarily associated with monocot families, such as Araceae, Arecaceae, Cyperaceae, Musaceae, Poaceae, Orchidaceae, and Zingiberaceae (Uhmann 1969; Jolivet and Hawkeswood 1995; Reid 1998; Schöller 2007, 2008; Staines 2015; Lee et al. 2012; Yang et al. 2023, 2024). Knowledge of the immature stages is sparse, with data available for only nine species (Lee et al. 2012). Research on their life history has been conducted by Chen (1929), Nair and Oommen (1965), Zaitsev (2001), and Lee et al. (2012). Eggs are laid either singly (Nair and Oommen 1965; Lee et al. 2012) or in small clusters (Chen 1929; Lee et al. 2012), and are encased in a membranous ootheca. Both larvae and adults feed openly on leaves, and pupation occurs directly on the leaves. In China, the genus *Callispa* is represented by 37 species (Sekerka & Świętojańska 2024).

Supported by the Guangdong Academy of Sciences and the Forestry Administration of Guangdong Province, extensive entomological surveys have been conducted in the Nanling Mountains and adjacent areas under the leadership of Prof. Xing-Ke Yang. Within the framework of this project, specimens of the genus *Callispa* collected from Guangdong Province were examined in detail. As a result, one species is recorded from Guangdong for the first time, and an updated checklist of eight *Callispa* species occurring in Guangdong Province is provided.

● Material and methods

All specimens were softened by soaking in room-temperature distilled water for 24 hours before being removed and positioned. Once a specimen was sufficiently softened, the abdomen was detached and opened to expose the genitalia. Male and female genitalia were extracted and placed in a 10% NaOH solution and heated in a water bath for 5 minutes. Afterward, the genitalia were rinsed thoroughly in distilled water and stored in glycerin.

Images were taken using a Canon EOS R5 mirrorless camera paired with a Canon EF 100 mm macro lens and a Canon MP-E 65 mm macro lens. Additional photographs were captured using a self-assembled bellows system mounted with Mitutoyo 10× and 20× APO objective lenses. Focus stacking was performed using a custom-built motorized rail system, and image stacks were processed with Helicon Focus V. 8.2.2. Final adjustments, including cropping and contrast enhancement, were conducted in Adobe Photoshop.

Abbreviations used herein: **TL** – type locality; **TD** – type depository.

Institutional abbreviations used herein:

BMNH The Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom;

CASC California Academy of Sciences, San Francisco, California, USA;

DEI Senckenberg Deutsches Entomologisches Institut, Müncheberg, Germany;

MNHN Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France;

IZCAS Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China;

USNM National Museum of Natural History, Washington D.C., USA.

● Taxonomy

Family Chrysomelidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily Cassidinae Gyllenhal, 1813

Tribe Callispini Chapuis, 1875

Genus *Callispa* Baly, 1858

Callispa Baly, 1858: 4. **Type species:** *Callispa fortunii* Baly, 1858, by original designation.

Miltinaspis Weise, 1904: 443. **Type species:** *Cephaloleia cassidoidea* Guérin-Méneville, 1844, by monotypy. Synonymized by Würmli 1975: 17.

Melispis Weise, 1897: 114. **Type species:** *Melispis andrewesi* Weise 1897, by monotypy. Synonymized by Würmli 1975: 17.

Rhinocassis Spaeth, 1905: 255. **Type species:** *Cephaloleia cassidoidea* Guérin-Méneville, 1844, by monotypy. Synonymized by Spaeth 1929: 30.

Callispa (*Callispella*) Spaeth, 1935: 255. **Type species:** *Callispa gracilicornis* Weise, 1910, by original designation.

Diagnosis. Body oval or ovate, convex; bright coloration, glossy dorsal and ventral surfaces. Head narrower than pronotum, vertex projecting or slightly raised between eyes; tongue-shaped stridulatory organ, covered by anterior edge of pronotum. Frons narrow, with fine longitudinal ridge between antennae, encircling mouthparts. Antennae medium, 1/3 body length, first antennomere barely exposed, third antennomere longest. Pronotum variable, square to trapezoidal, anterior narrower than base, lateral margins arcuate; central area convex, smooth or finely punctate; sides concave, coarser punctation. Scutellum small, square or pentagonal, rounded apex. Elytra wider than pronotum at base, shoulders prominent; lateral edges parallel or expanded medially, open margin noticeable; basal margin wide, distal margin narrow. Punctate rows organized, 10–12 rows in middle; 6th–8th rows diverging after shoulder, coarser punctation at base and shoulders, finer near suture and apex. First row of punctures in longitudinal groove. Abdomen with fine punctures; thoracic and abdominal ventral punctation distinct at base and lateral edges. Legs robust, fore tarsomere longest, basal tarsomeres of fore- and midlegs punctate, tibiae and tarsomeres densely setose ventrally.

Distribution. Oriental and Afrotropical regions.

Callispa dimidiatipennis Baly, 1858

Figs 1A–M

Callispa dimidiatipennis Baly, 1858: 7. **TL:** Northern India, **TD:** BMNH.

Callispa quadricollis Weise, 1897: 113. **TL:** Myanmar, Paungde, **TD:** BMNH. Synonymized by Maulik 1919: 56.

Callispa hypoenops Maulik, 1919: 60. **TL:** India, Assam, Naga Hills; Indochina (Ban Pan, Upper Mekong River), **TD:** BMNH. Synonymized by Medvedev 1992: 147.

Callispa latior Pic, 1924: 27. **TL:** Vietnam, Hoa-Binh, Lac Tho, **TD:** MNHN. Synonymized by Kimoto 1999: 98.

Callispa jeanvoinei Pic, 1927: 25. **TL:** Vietnam, Lao Cai, Chapa, **TD:** MNHN. Synonymized by Medvedev 1992: 147.

Callispa vicina Pic, 1927: 25. **TL:** Northern Vietnam, **TD:** Type lost. Synonymized by Kimoto 1999: 97.

Callispa vicina latithorax Pic, 1927: 25. **TL:** Vietnam, Lao Cai, Chapa, **TD:** MNHN.

Callispa dimidiatipennis recticollis Gressitt, 1938: 321. **TL:** China, Hainan, Ta Han, near Red Mist Mountain, **TD:** CASC.

Specimen examined. Guangdong, Chebaling Nature Reserve, Xiba (细坝), 2022.VII.26, sweep net, leg. Lin Meiyang, 1 ex; Guangdong, Deqing County, Yuecheng Town (悦城镇), Cuitang Village (翠塘村), 2024.V.6, N 23°07'42.94", E 112°07'28.48", alt. 13 m, leg. Fan Zongji, 1 ex; Guangdong, Dinghushan National Nature Reserve, Tonggu Xiatang'ao (下塘坳), 2025.VII.19, N 23°11'54.56", E 112°30'33.47", alt. 190 m, leg. Fan Zongji, 2 ex; Guangdong, Dinghushan National Nature Reserve, Tielukeng (铁炉坑), 2025.VII.27, N 23°09'39.57", E 112°30'29.63", alt. 175 m, leg. Fan Zongji, 1 ex.

Redescription. Body length 4.6–5.4 mm. Body slightly elongate-rectangular, deep reddish-brown; posterior half of elytra metallic purple-blue, with curved anterior margin.

Head reddish-brown, smooth, without punctures; slightly protruding between eyes. Mandibles large, black.

FIGURE 1. *Callispa dimidiatipennis* Baly, 1858. Habitus, habitat, and ecological images: **A–C** Male **A** dorsal view **B** ventral view **C** lateral view **D–F** Male genitalia **D** dorsal view **E** ventral view **F** lateral view **G–I** Female **G** dorsal view **H** ventral view **I** lateral view **J** Spermatheca **K** Habitat; mixed conifer–broadleaf forest **L** Mating on the leaves of the host plant **M** Feeding on the host plant *Thysanolaena latifolia* (Roxb. ex Hornem.) Honda. Scale bar: **A–C, G–I** 2 mm **D–F** 0.5 mm **J** 0.2 mm. (**K–M** photographs by Zong-Ji Fan)

Antennae almost black, with eleven antennomeres, about one third of body length, subequal in thickness throughout; antennomere I reddish brown, antennomere III longest, approximately equal in length to combined length of antennomeres I and II; antennomere IV slightly shorter than antennomere III, distinctly longer than each of antennomeres V to X; antennomere XI gradually tapered apically.

Pronotum rectangular, length/width ratio 2:1. Anterior margin slightly concave, width equal to head. Posterior margin convex, lateral margins parallel. Anterior angles rounded, posterior angles slightly narrowed, each with a trichobothrium. Central area convex, with fine, sparse punctures; sides with coarse punctation; hypomerion finely shagreened, with coarse and dense punctures; prosternal process inverted T-shaped, narrow basally and broadened apically, with a longitudinal depression on each side of the median area. Scutellum reddish-brown, lateral corners rounded, heart-shaped.

Elytra subrectangular, wider than pronotum at base; anterior margin curved. Elytral humeri prominent, middle slightly concave, apex of elytra rounded. Punctures in 11 rows, coarser in middle region, finer apically. Elytral epipleura well developed.

Ventral surface reddish-brown. First ventrite with coxal lines, divergent and extending beyond half the length; ventrites I–IV finely punctate and bearing short setae; terminal ventrite more finely and densely punctate, apically broadly rounded.

Femora and tibiae reddish-brown; tarsi brownish-yellow. Femora sometimes punctate. Tibiae with dense setae at apex. Protarsomere I asymmetrical, outer side larger.

Genitalia. Male genitalia strongly sclerotized; lateral view C-shaped, base broad, middle narrowed, apical one-third expanded, gradually tapering to apex; apex truncate, slightly concave medially. Female spermatheca pear-shaped, strongly sclerotized.

Distribution. China (Guangdong, Guangxi, Guizhou, Hunan, Hainan, Yunnan); India, Laos, Myanmar, Vietnam.

Host plants. *Indocalamus longiauritus* Handel-Mazzetti, *Indocalamus tessellatus* (Munro) Keng f., *Miscanthus sinensis* Anderss., *Saccharum arundinaceum* Retz. (Poaceae), *Thysanolaena latifolia* (Roxb. ex Hornem.) Honda.

***Callispa biarcuata* Chen et Yu, 1961**

Fig. 2A

Callispa biarcuata Chen et Yu, 1961: 460. **TL:** China, Guangdong, **TD:** IZCAS.

Distribution. China (Guangdong).

Host plant. Unknown.

***Callispa cyanea* Chen et Yu, 1961**

Fig. 2B

Callispa cyanea Chen et Yu, 1961: 461. **TL:** China, Yunnan, **TD:** IZCAS.

Callispa cyanea fukienica Chen et Yu, 1964: 108. **TL:** China, Fujian, **TD:** IZCAS.

Distribution. China (Guangdong, Fujian, Guangxi, Yunnan); Vietnam.

Host plant. Unknown.

FIGURE 2. Habitus of *Callispa* species from Guangdong Province, including two type specimens: **A** Holotype, *Callispa biarcuata* Chen et Yu, 1961 **B** Holotype, *Callispa cyanea* Chen et Yu, 1961 **C** *Callispa bowringii* Baly, 1858 **D** *Callispa flaveola* Uhmman, 1931 **E** *Callispa fortunii* Baly, 1858 **F** *Callispa karena* Maulik, 1919. Scale bar: 1 mm.

Callispa bowringii Baly, 1858

Fig. 2C

Callispa bowringii Baly, 1858: 5. **TL:** China, Hong Kong, **TD:** BMNH.

Callispa bowringi Baly: Gemminger et Harold, 1876: 3599. Misspelling.

Callispa bowringi atripes Pic, 1924: 27. **TL:** China, Fujian, **TD:** MNHN.

Callispa bowringii atripes Pic, 1924. Synonymized by Chen et al. 1986: 382.

Callispa proxima Baly, 1869: 364. **TL:** Thailand-Laos Mountains, **TD:** BMNH. Synonymized by Medvedev 1992: 145.

Distribution. China (Guangdong, Jiangsu, Shanghai, Hubei, Jiangxi, Fujian, Hainan, Hong Kong, Guangxi, Sichuan, Guizhou, Yunnan); Vietnam, Laos, Thailand, Philippines.

Host plants. *Arundinaria* sp., *Bambusa blumeana* Schult.f., *Neosinocalamus* sp., *Indocalamus tessellatus* (Munro) Keng f., *Phyllostachys nigra* var. *henonis* (Mitford) Rendle, *Phyllostachys propinqua* McClure, *Sinobambusa* sp. (Poaceae: Bambusoideae).

***Callispa cyanipennis* Pic, 1924**

Callispa cyanipennis Pic, 1924: 27. **TL:** China, **TD:** MNHN.

Distribution. China (Guangdong, Fujian).

Host plant. Unknown.

***Callispa flaveola* Uhmann, 1931**

Fig. 2D

Callispa flaveola Uhmann, 1931: 193. **TL:** Indonesia, Sumatra, Medan, **TD:** DEI.

Distribution. China (Guangdong, Yunnan); Indonesia, Vietnam.

Host plant. *Bambusa* sp. (Poaceae).

***Callispa fortunii* Baly, 1858**

Fig. 2E

Callispa fortunii Baly, 1858: 6. **TL:** North China, **TD:** BMNH.

Callispa fortuni fortuni Baly: Hua 2002: 288. Misspelling.

Callispa fortunii emarginata Gressitt, 1938: 322. **TL:** China, Hainan, **TD:** USNM.

Callispa ruficeps Pic, 1929: 139. **TL:** Vietnam, Hoa-Binh, **TD:** MNHN. Synonymized by Medvedev 1992: 146.

Distribution. China (Guangdong, Shandong, Anhui, Zhejiang, Jiangxi, Fujian, Hainan, Yunnan); Vietnam.

Host plant. *Bambusa* sp. (Poaceae).

***Callispa karena* Maulik, 1919**

Fig. 2F

Callispa karena Maulik, 1919: 62. **TL:** Myanmar (Kayin State); Vietnam (Northern region); Laos (Houay Ko, Luang Prabang, Xieng Khouang), **TD:** BMNH.

Distribution. China (Guangdong, Hainan, Yunnan); Vietnam, Laos, India, Myanmar.

Host plant. *Bambusa* sp. (Poaceae).

Key to *Callispa* species of Guangdong Province

- 1 Dorsal surface entirely metallic blue, or with purple or copper luster; head, thorax, and scutellum black.....2
- Dorsal surface at least partially pale, ranging from pale yellow to reddish-brown.....3
- 2 Vertex sharply narrow, slightly concave on both sides; lateral sides of the pronotum arched; lateral margins with a broad border, widest at the middle or slightly behind the middle.....*C. bowringii*
- Vertex wider, often with a transverse groove posterior; lateral sides of the pronotum arched; 12 rows of punctures along the middle of the elytra.....*C. cyanea*
- 3 Elytra entirely metallic blue-green, deep blue, purple, or black; pronotum orange, reddish-brown.....4
- Elytra at least partially pale or non-metallic.....6
- 4 Elytral punctures irregular, only aligned along the middle suture and after the shoulders; body relatively wide, elytra blue or blue-purple; body length 7.6–8.5 mm.....*C. karena*

- Elytral punctures aligned neatly, if not, body length less than 7 mm.....5
- 5 Lateral sides of the pronotum straight, slightly wavy along the margin, slightly narrowed at the front.....
.....*C. cyanipennis*
- Pronotum length and width ratio generally less than 2:1, front edge slightly concave; elytral punctures in the
7th and 8th rows forked before the middle.....*C. fortunii*
- 6 Elytra anterior 1/2 deep red, or reddish-brown, posterior 1/2 with metallic blue luster.....
.....*C. dimidiatipennis*
- Elytra mostly or entirely yellow to brownish-yellow.....7
- 7 Pronotum entirely yellow without dark spots; elytral punctures chaotic, sometimes with three irregular rows
identifiable.....*C. flaveola*
- Each elytron with a tiny black dot near the posterior middle, a large black arc-shaped spot on the side, opening
outward; two small black spots on the middle suture shared by both elytra.....*C. biarcuata*

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